

Table S1: Properties of the overall benchmark dataset

Dataset	Project	Description	# Instances	# Defects	Defects %	Class	Granularity	# F
AEEEM	EQ	OSGi framework	324	129	39.8	Java	Class	61
	IDT	IDE development	997	206	20.7			
	LC	Search Engine library	691	64	9.3			
	ML	Task management	1862	245	13.2			
NASA	PDE	Java	1497	209	14.0	C	Function	38
	CM1	Spacecraft instrument	327	42	12.8			
	MW1	A zero gravity experiment about combustion	251	25	10			
	PC1	Flight software for earth orbiting satellite	696	55	7.9			
	PC3	Flight software for earth orbiting satellite	1073	132	12.3			
Open-source Java systems	PC5	Java	1276	176	13.8	Java	Class	20
	ant-1.7	Open-source	745	166	22			
	camel-1.6	Open-source	965	188	19			
	jedit-4.1	Open-source	312	79	25			
	lucene-2.4	Open-source	340	203	60			
	ivy-2.0	Open-source	354	40	11			
	poi-3.0	Open-source	442	281	64			

In Table S1, columns # Instances, # Defect, Defects % and # F represent the number of modules, number of the defective module, percentage of defective modules, and the number of features respectively.